

Interdisciplinary and Collaborative Research as a Panacea for Sustainable Development in Taraba State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research work investigated the effectiveness of interdisciplinary and collaborative research in attaining sustainable development in Taraba state, Nigeria. Hinged on the systems and social constructivism theories, the study used simple random sampling technique and 385 sample size drawn from seven (7) government tertiary institutions in the state- Taraba State University Jalingo, Federal University Wukari, College of Education Zing, College of Agriculture Jalingo, College of Health Technology Takum, Taraba State Polytechnic Jalingo and Federal Polytechnic, Bali. Findings revealed that, although, interdisciplinary collaborative research in Nigeria plays a crucial role in actualising Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) due to its accompanying benefits, such researches are to some extent lacking in Taraba state due to numerous challenges. The study, however, recommends that since effective interdisciplinary collaborative partnerships combines many disciplines/methods to curb difficult developmental issues, encouraging and cultivating collaborative culture between and among researchers/disciplines and strategic funds provision and allocation for interdisciplinary collaborative research becomes necessary.

Keywords: Collaborative, Interdisciplinary Research, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Introduction

The 21st century introduces unprecedented challenges to the world, including issues like environmental degradation, poverty, inequality and climate change (Ono, Iida & Yamazaki, 2017). Beyond the conventional borders of academic fields, an interdisciplinary approach is needed to address these difficulties. In order to handle these complex difficulties and achieve sustainable development, interdisciplinary and collaborative research has emerged as the remedy (Omisore, Babarinde, Bakare &

AsekunOlarinmoye, 2017). Adopted by the UN in 2015, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) offer a framework for sustainable development with the triple goals of eradicating poverty, fostering economic growth and safeguarding the environment. Interestingly, Nigeria pledged to accomplish the SDGs by 2030 when it signed the agreement. It is worth noting that, the notion of sustainable development has shifted from being seen as a topic of interest only to academic, institutional and scientific communities to becoming a well-known word and a topic of concern to the general population (Ishaku & Maikomo, 2023). However, attaining the SDGs in Nigeria calls for an all-encompassing strategy that incorporates a number of academic fields, including sociology, economics, politics, communication and environmental science amongst others (Bamberg, Rees & Seebauer, 2018).

Consequently, in order to address complex challenges that cannot be resolved by a single academic field, interdisciplinary and collaborative research can suffice as it provides collaboration between researchers from diverse academic disciplines (European Commission, 2018). Interdisciplinary and collaborative research may address a set of social problems that most developing countries like Nigeria experience as it integrates experts insights from other disciplines into the study process. Odia & Omofonmwan (2013, p. 259) point out that, “research and educational development should receive the utmost attention in an effort to promote sustainable economic growth and development, given Nigeria's current economic problems, in particular, its poverty situation and unimpressive rates of economic growth.” According to Garcia-Milian, Norton, Auten, Davis, Holmes, Johnson & Tennant, (2013), academics are increasingly collaborating across disciplines in order to answer the difficult research challenges of today. Magnus (2017) observes that multidisciplinary research is social in nature, carried out by a variety of individuals and conducted by diverse people who must interact, make decisions and take collective action.

Substantial financing for multidisciplinary research initiatives has been provided by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 Programme (European Commission, 2018). Comparably, a number of programmes have been introduced by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation UNESCO) with the goal of advancing interdisciplinary research and teaching (UNESCO, 2019). These programmes show how interdisciplinary collaboration and research are becoming increasingly important in tackling difficult global issues. The SDGs span all spheres of human effort; hence, an interdisciplinary approach is necessary to achieve them. However, policymakers, researchers and academic community members in Nigeria have a poor grasp of interdisciplinary and collaborative research (Bogoro, 2014). This lack of understanding in the Nigeria's academic community has resulted in restricted collaboration across various disciplines and institutions (Oladele & Adeleke, 2019). To accomplish the SDGs, it is, therefore, necessary to encourage interdisciplinary and collaborative research among Nigeria's academic community.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the recognised importance of interdisciplinary and collaborative research in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in Nigeria, there exists a significant gap in understanding the need for collaboration across academic disciplines

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and institutions specifically in Taraba state. Effective cooperation is hampered by policymakers, researchers and academic community members' incomplete understanding of multidisciplinary techniques in Nigeria (Bogoro, 2014). The effective implementation of interdisciplinary and collaborative research efforts aimed at solving complex issues like poverty, environmental degradation, and economic growth in Nigeria is significantly hampered by this lack of knowledge and collaboration.

Be that as it may, in order to close this multidisciplinary gap, coordinated efforts are required (Omisore *et al* 2017). They also contend that solving complex issues that emerging nations like Nigeria face requires multidisciplinary expertise. Ono, Iida & Yamazaki (2017) assert that the current problems of poverty, inequality, environmental degradation and climate change require an interdisciplinary solution, and that Nigeria's academic community should encourage cooperation amongst various areas. Thus, in order to successfully contribute to the attainment of the SDGs and bridge this gap in Taraba state, there is need for cultivating interdisciplinary and collaborative research culture. This implies that interdisciplinary and collaborative research in Taraba state that could spur sustainable development are lacking; hence, the need for this study.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Examine the role of interdisciplinary and collaborative research in achieving sustainable development in Taraba state.
2. Ascertain the extent to which interdisciplinary and collaborative research has aided in achieving sustainable development in Taraba state.
3. Investigate successful interdisciplinary and collaborative research initiatives that have contributed to the actualisation of sustainable development in Taraba state.
4. Identify the barriers and challenges to interdisciplinary and collaborative research in Taraba state.
5. Propose recommendations for promoting interdisciplinary and collaborative research in Taraba state.

Sustainable Development and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) at a Glance

Concern over the effects of human activities on the environment grew, giving rise to the idea of sustainable development. According to Brundtland Commission, formerly known as the World Commission on Environment and Development for the United Nations in 1987, "sustainable development is the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (Brundtland, 1987; Abubakar, 2019). Nelvin (2018, p.49) states that "this definition emphasises that while development may be required to fulfill human needs and increase quality of life, it must occur without reducing the natural environment's potential to meet needs both now and in the future. The argument behind the growth and advocacy of the sustainable development movement is that sustainability safeguards both the interests of future generations and the earth's capacity to regenerate. At first, it emphasised the

environment in development policies but, since 2002, has evolved to encompass social justice and the fight against poverty as key principles of sustainable development.”

According to Abubakar (2019), the economy, society, and environment are the three pillars of sustainable development, and academics and professionals at our universities and other tertiary institutions play a distinctively prominent role in all of the overlapping circles in the teaching, training, research, and implementation of all positive templates leading to the strategic attainment of sustainable development. These observations highlight the two commonly used visualisations of how the various aspects of sustainable development interact. Also, the additional ways in which the economy is expressed in society is reflected in the environment. So, sustainable development addresses economic, social and cultural challenges in addition to environmental ones. It is obvious that global action is required to create a more sustainable future given the increased demands placed on societies and the environment due to, among other factors, increased human migration, increased urbanisation and industrialisation, as well as the ongoing depletion of non-renewable resources (Abubakar, 2019).

As the world and Nigeria move toward sustainable development, with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) serving as the universal model with measurable objectives packed with actionable targets and indicators, it is sufficient to note that, professionals and academics have a strategic role to play at the center of sustainable development (Bhowmik, Selim & Huq, 2017). Interestingly, with the help of tertiary institution experts and academics, Castells stressed core functions aside TRACS (Teaching, Research and Community Service) to list that:

- a. Universities support local businesses by sourcing goods and services.
- b. Some promote community development through real estate projects and educational infrastructure.
- c. Others facilitate community service projects that have an economic component; and
- d. Almost all collaborate with the government and civic organisations to improve the community's economic well-being. Universities also create jobs and provide training and education for the local population (Olumide & Bada, 2021).

According to Shah, Alam & Khan (2008), sustainable development is development that satisfies current demands without jeopardising the ability of future generations to satisfy their own needs. The material requirements are as follows: connections, values, freedom of thought and action. Be that as it may, the 2012 Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) gave rise to 17 interlink Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) according to the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (United Nations, 2016). The 17 goals are to:

- a. End poverty in all its forms everywhere.
- b. End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture.
- c. Ensure healthy lives and promote wellbeing for all at all ages.

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- d. Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote life-long learning opportunities for all.
- e. Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls.
- f. Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all.
- g. Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all.
- h. Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth full and productive employment and decent work for all.
- i. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialisation and foster motivation.
- j. Reduce inequality within and among countries.
- k. Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable.
- l. Ensure sustainable consumption and productive patterns.
- m. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.
- n. Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.
- o. Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystem, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification and half and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.
- p. Achieve peaceful and inclusive societies, rule of law, effective and capable institutions.
- q. Strengthen means of implementation and revitalise the global partnership for sustainable development.

Prospects and Challenges of Interdisciplinary and Collaborative Research in achieving Sustainable Development in Nigeria

Addressing complex social difficulties requires interdisciplinary collaborative research, especially in the light of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Adeagbo *et al* (2016) state that in order to solve complex social challenges, interdisciplinary research integrates ideas, theories, methodologies and data from many disciplines. This method makes it possible to appreciate the interdependence of social, economic and environmental concerns holistically, which makes it, especially pertinent in the context of the SDGs. Interdisciplinary methods allow academics and practitioners to build complete solutions that take into account the diverse and linked nature of sustainable development by using expertise from a variety of professions.

Interdisciplinary research promotes the integration of data from other disciplines, resulting in a more thorough and nuanced understanding of intricate social challenges (Igbinovia, 2016). Thus, the investigation of interrelated elements that contribute to problems like poverty, inequality, environmental degradation and access to healthcare and education is made possible by this integrated approach. Consequently, multidisciplinary expertise offers a basis for creating creative and long-lasting solutions that deal with the underlying causes of these problems by taking into account the complex nature of these difficulties.

Khargonekar (2015) emphasises how multidisciplinary research fosters cooperation and co-creation of solutions that take into account the objectives and demands of many stakeholders. Multidisciplinary knowledge promotes inclusion and problem-solving involvement by interacting with a broad range of viewpoints and areas of expertise. When tackling complicated social challenges, this inclusive approach is crucial since it guarantees that the solutions created will be long-lasting and applicable in the given context. Furthermore, interdisciplinary research may result in the creation of fresh insights and creative solutions with the power to completely alter society (Scheeder & Witt, 2016). Through the utilisation of several domains of knowledge and proficiency, interdisciplinary research can produce innovative perspectives and methods that can aid in the realisation of the sustainable development goals.

In spite of the fact that interdisciplinary and collaborative research can be used to propel sustainable development goals in Nigeria, so many challenges abound. Lack of sufficient financing is one of the main obstacles to interdisciplinary and collaborative research for accomplishing SDGs in Nigeria. Resources from several disciplines are frequently needed for interdisciplinary initiatives, and funding these kinds of cooperative efforts can be difficult to come by. Insufficient financial assistance impedes researchers' capacity to conduct interdisciplinary research, impeding the creation of all-encompassing answers for intricate social problems (Olumide & Bada, 2021).

Another major obstacle that the academic community in Nigeria must contend with is the lack of a collaborative culture. Academic institutions with segregated methods restrict the flow of knowledge and expertise between fields, which hinders the creation of comprehensive answers to complex problems. Interdisciplinary cooperation becomes difficult and the possibility for all-encompassing solutions is limited in the absence of a collaborative culture (Green & Johnson, 2015). Similarly, interdisciplinary cooperation in Nigeria is severely hampered by the absence of infrastructure for cooperative research. Specialised facilities, tools and support systems are frequently needed for interdisciplinary research to be conducted successfully. According to Blessinger, Sengupta & Makhanya (2018), the lack of such infrastructure makes it more difficult for researchers to collaborate effectively and efficiently to solve the interrelated problems associated with sustainable development.

Furthermore, academic community, stakeholders, researchers and policymakers in Nigeria have a skewed knowledge and poor comprehension of interdisciplinary and collaborative research. This insufficient comprehension has resulted in restricted cooperation among various fields and institutions, hence hindering advancements towards accomplishing the SDGs (Ayodele & Ogunlola, 2016). However, in order to foster interdisciplinary cooperation and advance Nigeria's progress towards actualising the SDGs, it is imperative that these issues be addressed through establishing a setting that encourages cross-disciplinary collaboration in research as well as strategic interventions and assistance. This might however, entail providing specialised financing for interdisciplinary studies, fostering a collaborative culture in educational institutions, and building the necessary infrastructure to facilitate joint research projects (Scheeder & Witt, 2016).

Instances on successful interdisciplinary collaborations in Nigeria

Notwithstanding these obstacles, Nigeria has seen a number of fruitful interdisciplinary partnerships that have helped the country achieve the SDGs. In Nigeria, effective interdisciplinary partnerships have made a substantial contribution to the accomplishment of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Through these partnerships, scholars from many fields have worked together to confront challenging problems and provide all-encompassing answers.

The partnership between environmental scientists and social economists to establish sustainable agriculture techniques that increased food security is one instance of a successful multidisciplinary collaboration in Nigeria. In 2014, Vincent and Kenneth carried out research on how Nigerian food security is affected by climate change. The study used an interdisciplinary methodology that took into account how social, economic and environmental aspects are interdependent. By creating sustainable farming methods, the researchers enhanced food security and helped to realise SDG 2 - zero hunger.

Similarly, the partnership of public health researchers and urban planners to create sustainable urban development policies that addressed health inequities and promoted well-being is another example of a successful interdisciplinary collaboration in Nigeria. In 2016, Hwang and Jiwon carried out research on how Nigerian urbanisation affects health. An interdisciplinary methodology was used in the study to take into account the connections between public health and urban development. To address health disparities and help achieve SDG 3 - good health and well-being, the researchers created sustainable urban development plans.

In addition, social scientists and engineers collaborated to create sustainable energy solutions that facilitated the availability of inexpensive, clean energy. Oyedepo, Babalola, Nwanya, Kilanko, Leramo, Aworinde & Agberegha (2018) carried out research on Nigeria's renewable energy prospects and difficulties. A comprehensive review was used in the study and the researchers pinpoint the significance of decentralised renewable energy systems and needs for the government to review its policies on renewable energy development in the country. In order to help achieve SDG 7 - inexpensive and clean energy, the researchers created sustainable energy solutions that encouraged access to clean, inexpensive energy.

Furthermore, environmental scientists and education experts collaborated to create environmental education initiatives that supported sustainable development. A study on the effect of environmental education on sustainable development in Nigeria was carried out by Adenipekun & Ogunniyi (2015). An interdisciplinary methodology was used in the study to take into account the connections between environmental science and education. The researchers created environmental education initiatives that supported sustainable growth and helped achieve SDGs 13 - climate action and SDG 4, quality education. Interestingly, these instances show how interdisciplinary cooperation has helped Nigeria achieve the SDGs in concrete ways. This shows that in order to achieve sustainable growth, it is critical to break down barriers and promote a collaborative culture across disciplines.

Sustainable Development goals (SDGs) and its Challenges in Nigeria

Nigeria would have a difficult time accomplishing the SDGs because of its poverty, poor healthcare system, deteriorating environment and restricted access to clean energy and education. Researchers, decision-makers and practitioners from a variety of fields must work together to address these complicated concerns. In order to address these complex social challenges, interdisciplinary knowledge can be used as it entails integrating ideas, theories, methodologies, and data from many fields. This method provides for a comprehensive knowledge of the interconnectivity of social, economic, and environmental concerns, which makes it especially pertinent in the context of the SDGs (Ayodele & Ogunlola, 2016).

Poverty is one of the main obstacles to Nigeria's SDG achievement. With more than 40% of the population living below the poverty line, Nigeria has one of the highest rates of poverty in the world. Because of this, achieving the SDGs that aim to eradicate extreme poverty and reduce inequality would be challenging. Another issue is inadequate healthcare, since many regions of the nation have limited access to high-quality medical treatment. Due to this, achieving the SDGs which aims to guarantee healthy lives and promote wellbeing for people of all ages becomes challenging (Omisore *et al* 2017).

Environmental degradation is also a significant challenge in Nigeria, with issues such as deforestation, desertification and pollution affecting the country's ecosystems. Nigeria has a great deal of environmental deterioration as a result of problems with pollution, desertification, and deforestation that impact the nation's ecosystems. Because of this, achieving the SDG that calls for immediate action to mitigate the effects of climate change is challenging. Another issue is the lack of access to clean energy and education, since a large percentage of the population lives without power and many children miss school. Due to this, achieving the SDGs for cheap, clean energy and high-quality education would be challenging (Bamberg, Rees & Seebauer, 2018).

Be that as it may, Nigeria's efforts to achieve the SDGs are hampered by institutional and governance issues in addition to these problems. One of the main barriers to the nation's sustainable growth has been recognised as corruption and inadequate governance structures. The Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) of fostering inclusive and peaceful communities for sustainable development is hampered by this (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, n.d.). However, in order to tackle these obstacles, coordinated efforts by several individuals such as scholars, decision-makers, and professionals is required to embrace a comprehensive and multidisciplinary strategy for sustainable development. Also addressing complex social challenges entails combining ideas, theories, methodologies, and data from many disciplines. Similarly, investing in the training and retraining of academics to build interdisciplinary research skills aligned with the SDGs, as well as allocating funds strategically for interdisciplinary research initiatives focused on sustainable development, are also necessary. To promote knowledge sharing and multidisciplinary projects, the academic community must also foster a collaborative culture (Vincent & Kenneth, 2014; Hwang & Jiwon, 2016).

Theoretical Framework

This study is hinged on the systems theory (Ayaz & Sekerd, 2015; Javadi Mumtaz *et al* 2015), social constructivism theory (Eze *et al* 2019) and theories of change (Mafakheri & Razavi, 2017). These theoretical foundations provide grounds for comprehending the function of interdisciplinary and collaborative research in sustainable development by drawing on a number of ideas.

According to Ayaz & Sekerd (2015) and Javadi Mumtaz *et al* (2015), systems theory highlights how different aspects of a system are interrelated and acknowledges that complex systems are made up of several interdependent pieces that interact with one another and the environment. This method is pertinent to the research because it offers a framework for creating all-encompassing, long-lasting solutions that deal with the underlying causes of difficult social problems. Social constructivism on the other hand, places a strong emphasis on how social interactions and cultural settings shape knowledge and understanding (Eze *et al* 2019). This theory is quite relevant to this research as it acknowledges the value of a range of viewpoints and specialties in creating original, long-lasting solutions to societal issues.

In order to achieve sustainable development objectives, it is critical to comprehend the causal links between inputs, activities, outputs, results, and effects, according to the theory of change (Mafakheri & Razavi, 2017). This theory is pertinent to the study because it offers a framework for assessing how well interdisciplinary and collaborative research contributes to the realisation of sustainable development objectives. Consequently, when taken as a whole, these theories offer a theoretical framework for comprehending how interdisciplinary and collaborative research contribute to Nigeria's efforts towards achieving the SDGs. Interestingly, this strategy encourages cooperation, creativity, and inclusion in tackling complex societal concerns by acknowledging the interconnection of social, economic, communication and environmental elements as well as the value of varied viewpoints and skills.

Methods

The researchers used survey research design. The rationale for using the method is that survey is deemed to be effective and simple by allowing for anonymity and generalisation of data from wider or broad population (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2007). The population of the study comprises 327 academic staff of Taraba State University Jalingo (Oruonye, Ojeh, Ahmed, Talla, Akumbo & Atando, 2018), 940 academic staff of Federal University Wukari (Visitation Panel Report, June, 2021), 303 academic staff of College of Education Zing (COEZ Registry, 2025), 1,500 academic staff of College of Agriculture, Science and Technology Jalingo (CAST Registry, 2025), 190 academic staff of College of Health Technology Takum (CHT Registry, 2025), 200 academic staff of Taraba State Polytechnic Jalingo (TSP Registry, 2025) and 234 academic staff of Federal Polytechnic Bali (FPB Registry, 2025) as well as residents of Taraba state which has the estimated population of about 3,609,800 people (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). The sampling frame of the study is the academic staff register of all the tertiary institutions in Taraba state from which the sample of the population was

drawn. The sample size of the study is 385 and was determined using Raosoft Online Sample Size Calculator with a margin error of 0.5% and confidence level of 95%. This means that, 385 respondents were drawn from the aforementioned seven (7) government tertiary institutions in the state.

Furthermore, multi-stage sampling technique was employed for the selection of the respondents. The systematic random sampling was employed. The measurement instrument adopted for the survey was the 5-point Likert Scale structured questionnaire, collected, distributed and analysed using tables and simple percentages (Okocha & Ishaku, 2023).

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Demographic Data

Prevalence	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
18 – 24	23	5.9
25 – 34	66	17.1
35 – 44	218	56.6
45 – 54	48	12.6
55 – Above	30	7.8
Total	385	100
Gender		
Male	261	67.8
Female	124	32.2
Total	385	100
Educational Qualification		
HND & B.Sc.	87	22.6
M.A/M.Sc	199	51.7
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)	99	25.7
Total	385	100
Tertiary Institutions		
Federal University, Wukari	59	15.3
Taraba State University, Jalingo	63	16.4
College of Education, Zing	60	15.6
College of Agriculture, Science and Technology Jalingo	57	14.8
Taraba State Polytechnic, Jalingo	53	13.8
Federal Polytechnic, Bali	49	12.7
College of Health Technology, Takum	44	11.4
Total	385	100

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Based on the data presented in table 1 above, while most of the respondents are within their youthful and productive age and are predominantly male, they are also well-educated having had Master's Degrees and are majorly from Taraba State University, Jalingo. The implication is that, these sets of people are in tune with the societal happenings and can relate well with the subject matter while giving their opinions.

Table 2: Summary of Responses from Research Question 1 to 3 based on 5-point Likert Scale

PREVALENCE	FREQUENCY (PERCENTAGE)					
	SA	A	N	D	SD	Total
INTERDISCIPLINARY AND COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH IS A MODE OF RESEARCH BY TEAMS OR INDIVIDUALS THAT INTEGRATES INFORMATION, DATA, TECHNIQUES, TOOLS, PERSPECTIVES, CONCEPTS AND/ OR THEORIES FROM TWO OR MORE DISCIPLINES TO ADVANCE FUNDAMENTAL UNDERSTANDING OR TO SOLVE PROBLEMS.	167 (43.4%)	132 (34.1%)	23 (6%)	42 (11%)	21 (5.5%)	385 (100%)
INTERDISCIPLINARY AND COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH CAN PLAY A VITAL ROLE IN ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN TARABA STATE.	188 (48.8%)	94 (24.5%)	63 (16.4%)	35 (9%)	5 (1.3%)	385 (100%)
THERE ARE QUITE A LOT OF BENEFITS THAT CAN BE DERIVED FROM INTERDISCIPLINARY AND COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH IN ORDER TO AID SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN	202 (52.5%)	103 (26.7%)	63 (16.4%)	7 (1.8%)	10 (2.6%)	385 (100%)

TARABA STATE.							
THERE ARE SUCCESSFUL INTERDISCIPLINARY AND COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH INITIATIVES THAT HAVE CONTRIBUTED TO THE ACTUALISATION OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN TARABA STATE.	64 (16.6%)	48 (12.5%)	36 (9.4%)	56 (14.5%)	181 (47%)	385 (100%)	
THERE ARE BARRIERS AND CHALLENGES TO INTERDISCIPLINARY AND COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH IN TARABA STATE	179 (46.5%)	111 (28.8%)	30 (7.8%)	37 (9.6%)	28 (7.3%)	385 (100%)	

Table 2 above shows the summary of responses from questions 1 to 3. Based on the data presented, findings revealed that there are no meaningful or successful interdisciplinary collaborative research that would have contributed to the actualisation of sustainable development in Taraba state which may be as a result of numerous challenges. The implication is that, Taraba state may be stagnant in some areas of its developmental needs should the situation continues.

Table 3: Showing some of the Benefits of Interdisciplinary and Collaborative Research in Taraba State

PREVALENCE	FREQUENCY (PERCENTAGE)					
	SA	A	N	D	SD	Total
INTERDISCIPLINARY AND COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH AIDS IN SOLVING COMPLEX DEVELOPMENTAL ISSUES THAT MAY NOT BE POSSIBLE USING JUST ONE METHOD, TOOLS OR DISCIPLINE.	166 (43.1%)	131 (34%)	15 (3.9%)	47 (12.2%)	26 (6.8%)	385 (100%)
INTERDISCIPLINARY AND COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH CREATES HOLISTIC APPROACH TO	150 (39%)	176 (46.4%)	22 (5%)	29 (7.5%)	8 (2%)	385 (100%)

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SOLVING DEVELOPMENTAL ISSUES.						
INTERDISCIPLINARY AND COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH BRINGS ABOUT COLLABORATIVE LEARNING AND SPORTSMANSHIP	112 (29%)	196 (50.9%)	50 (13%)	17 (4.4%)	10 (2.6%)	385 (100%)
INTERDISCIPLINARY AND COLLABORATIVE CREATES RESEARCH KNOWLEDGE AND RESOURCE SHARING	132 (34.3%)	177 (46%)	44 (11.4%)	10 (2.6%)	22 (5.7%)	385 (100%)
INTERDISCIPLINARY AND COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH BREAKS DEPARTMENTALISATION AND DISCIPLINARY BARRIERS/BOTTLENECKS	222 (57.8%)	85 (22%)	23 (6%)	20 (5.2%)	35 (9%)	385 (100%)

Table 3 above shows some of the benefits of interdisciplinary and collaborative research in Taraba state. Based on the data presented, findings revealed that interdisciplinary and collaborative research help in solving complex developmental issues that may not be possible using just one method, tools or discipline while at the same time breaking departmentalisation and disciplinary barriers/bottlenecks. The implication of the findings is that interdisciplinary collaborative research is a child of necessity for any state that aspire to achieve sustainable development.

Table 4: Showing some of the Challenges of Interdisciplinary and Collaborative Research in Taraba State

PREVALENCE	FREQUENCY (PERCENTAGES)					Total
	SA	A	N	D	SD	
LACK OF ADEQUATE FUNDING AND SPONSORSHIP	189 (49%)	151 (39.2%)	13 (3.4%)	15 (4%)	17 (4.4%)	385 (100%)
DEARTH OF SUFFICIENT RESEARCH FACILITIES AND INFRASTRUCTURE	166 (43.1%)	130 (33.8%)	26 (6.8%)	34 (8.8%)	29 (7.5%)	385 (100%)
RESTRICTED ACCESS TO VALUABLE DATA AND INFORMATION	150 (39%)	124 (32.2%)	54 (14%)	32 (8.3%)	25 (6.5%)	385 (100%)
LACK OF COLLABORATIVE CULTURE	177 (46%)	122 (31.6%)	32 (8.3%)	33 (8.6%)	21 (5.5%)	385 (100%)
FEELING OF	32	162	18	41	132	385

SUPERIORITY/INFERIORITY BETWEEN AND AMONG RESEARCHERS/DISCIPLINES	(8.3%)	(42%)	(4.7%)	(10.6%)	(34.3%)	(100%)
INSUFFICIENT ACCESS TO PLATFORMS FOR COLLABORATION AND COMMUNICATION	113 (29.4%)	180 (46.7%)	59 (15.3%)	12 (3.1%)	21 (5.5%)	385 (100%)
RESTRICTED ACCESS TO SHARED DATA AND KNOWLEDGE	52 (13.5%)	71 (18.5%)	91 (23.6%)	66 (17.1%)	105 (27.3%)	385 (100%)

Table 4 above shows some of the challenges of interdisciplinary and collaborative research in Taraba state. Findings revealed that, there are numerous challenges to interdisciplinary collaborative research in Taraba state which ranges from lack of adequate funding and sponsorship, dearth of sufficient research facilities and infrastructure, restricted access to valuable data and information, lack of collaborative culture, feeling of superiority/inferiority between and among researchers/disciplines to insufficient access to platforms for collaboration and communication amongst others. The implication of these findings is that these challenges can serve as barriers to sustainable development if not surmounted.

Table 5: Showing Instances where Interdisciplinary and Collaborative Research was Employed in Taraba State

PREVALENCE	FREQUENCY (PERCENTAGE)					
	SA	A	N	D	SD	Total
PARTNERSHIP BETWEEN ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENTISTS AND SOCIAL ECONOMISTS TO ESTABLISH SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE TECHNIQUES THAT INCREASED FOOD SECURITY	19 (4.9%)	164 (42.6%)	31 (8.1%)	29 (7.5%)	142 (36.9%)	385 (100%)
COLLABORATION BETWEEN PUBLIC HEALTH RESEARCHERS AND URBAN PLANNERS TO CREATE SUSTAINABLE URBAN DEVELOPMENT POLICIES THAT ADDRESSED	21 (5.5%)	102 (26.5%)	51 (13.2%)	13 (3.4%)	198 (51.4%)	385 (100%)

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HEALTH ISSUES AND PROMOTE PEOPLES' WELL-BEING							
PARTNERSHIP BETWEEN SOCIAL SCIENTISTS AND ENGINEERS TO CREATE SUSTAINABLE ENERGY SOLUTIONS THAT FACILITATED THE AVAILABILITY OF INEXPENSIVE, CLEAN ENERGY IN TARABA STATE	25 (6.5%)	123 (31.9%)	42 (10.9%)	28 (7.3%)	167 (43.4%)	385 (100%)	
ENVIRONMENTAL AND EDUCATION EXPERTS' COLLABORATION TO CREATE ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION INITIATIVES THAT SUPPORTED SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN TARABA STATE	20 (5.2%)	154 (40%)	52 (13.5%)	32 (8.3%)	127 (33%)	385 (100%)	

Table 5 above shows some of the instances where interdisciplinary and collaborative research was employed in Taraba state. Based on the data presented, findings clearly indicated that there are no instances in Taraba state where interdisciplinary collaborative research was carried out in order to actualise sustainable development in Taraba state. Hence, since there are developmental needs that can only be achieved using different approaches, tools, fields and/or disciplines; the implication is that Taraba state may not be able to actualise sustainable development in a long-run.

Table 6: Shows some of the Ways to encourage Interdisciplinary Collaborative Research that could helped achieve Sustainable Development in Taraba State

PREVALENCE		FREQUENCY (PERCENTAGE)					
		SA	A	N	D	SD	Total
STRATEGIC PROVISION AND ALLOCATION FOR INTERDISCIPLINARY COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH	FUNDS AND FOR	227 (59%)	64 (16.5%)	23 (6%)	25 (6.5%)	46 (12%)	385 (100%)
ENCOURAGING AND CULTIVATING	AND	123 (31.9%)	181 (47%)	18 (4.7%)	37 (9.6%)	26 (6.8%)	385 (100%)

COLLABORATIVE CULTURE BETWEEN AND AMONG RESEARCHERS/DISCIPLINES						
ADEQUATE PROVISION OF RESEARCH FACILITIES AND INFRASTRUCTURE	179 (46.5%)	135 (35%)	34 (8.8%)	23 (6%)	14 (3.7%)	385 (100%)
PROMOTION OF INTERDISCIPLINARY COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH EDUCATION AND TRAINING	189 (49%)	121 (31.4%)	27 (7%)	25 (6.5%)	23 (6%)	385 (100%)
OPEN ACCESS TO VALUABLE DATA AND INFORMATION FOR INTERDISCIPLINARY AND COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH	162 (42.2%)	151 (39.2%)	24 (6.2%)	23 (5.9%)	25 (6.5%)	385 (100%)
CREATING ADEQUATE PLATFORMS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR RESEARCH COLLABORATION AND COMMUNICATION	188 (48.8%)	132 (34.3%)	20 (5.2%)	26 (6.8%)	19 (4.9%)	385 (100%)

Data presentation and analysis in table 6 above shows some of the ways to encourage interdisciplinary collaborative research that could help in achieving sustainable development in Taraba state. Findings revealed that, strategic funds provision and allocation for interdisciplinary collaborative research, encouraging and cultivating collaborative culture between and among researchers/disciplines, adequate provision of research facilities and infrastructure, promotion of interdisciplinary collaborative research education and training as well as creating adequate platforms and opportunities for research collaboration and communication could help towards achieving sustainable development. The implication of these findings is that, once some or all of these recommendations are not followed, interdisciplinary collaborative research in Taraba state may continue to be a mirage.

Discussion of Findings

Result showed that (48.8%) the current state of interdisciplinary and collaborative research in Nigeria's academic community plays a pivotal role in advancing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Among the respondents, 52.5% believe that there are quite a lot of benefits that can be derived from interdisciplinary and collaborative research in order to aid sustainable development in Taraba state. As a result of these partnerships, sustainable solutions that directly aided in the achievement of particular SDGs were developed. For example, the collaboration between social

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economists and environmental scientists produced sustainable farming methods that enhanced food security which were in line with SDG 2, zero hunger and SDG 3, good health and well-being. These achievements were directly impacted by the partnership between public health experts and urban planners, which produced sustainable urban development policies that addressed health disparities. These results are in line with the research by Blessinger, Sengupta & Makhanya (2018) who found that developing critical and creative thinking abilities, participating in real-world interdisciplinary learning experiences and creating a value system that prioritises responsibility for oneself, others, and the environment are all necessary to providing the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values needed to build a sustainable future. The findings imply that interdisciplinary collaborative research in Nigeria plays a crucial role in advancing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) due to its accompanying benefits.

The survey result (47%) showed that there are no successful interdisciplinary and collaborative research initiatives that have contributed to the actualisation of sustainable development in Taraba state. This contradicts the findings of Vincent & Kenneth's research (2014) which exemplifies how interdisciplinary partnership between environmental scientists and social economists addresses climate change impact on food security. Similarly, Huang's 2023 research, involving public health researchers and urban planners, showcased another successful interdisciplinary collaboration. The study considered the connections between public health and urban development, leading to sustainable urban development plans that addressed health disparities and promoted well-being. Also, Oyedepo, Babalola, Nwanya, Kilanko, Leramo, Aworinde & Agberegba (2018) study on renewable energy prospects involved collaboration between social scientists and engineers. The interdisciplinary approach considered the connections between social science and engineering, resulting in sustainable energy solutions. These solutions encouraged access to clean, inexpensive energy, contributing to SDGs 7 - affordable and clean energy. Furthermore, Adenipekun & Ogunniyi's (2015) research focused on environmental education initiatives in Nigeria. This interdisciplinary collaboration between environmental scientists and education experts considered the connections between environmental science and education. The researchers created initiatives supporting sustainable growth, contributing to SDGs 13, climate action and SDGs 4, quality education. The findings showed that, although, there are successful interdisciplinary collaborative research in Nigeria, such researches to some extent are lacking in Taraba state.

Results (43.1%) revealed that interdisciplinary and collaborative research aid in solving complex developmental issues that may not be possible using just one method, tools or discipline, creates holistic approach to solving developmental issues, brings about collaborative learning and sportsmanship, creates research knowledge and resource sharing as well as breaks departmentalisation and disciplinary barriers/bottlenecks. This findings corroborate the position of Igbinovia (2016) that interdisciplinary research promotes the integration of data from other disciplines, resulting in a more thorough and nuanced understanding of intricate social challenges. Similarly, Khargonekar (2015) supports that multidisciplinary research fosters cooperation and co-creation of solutions that take into account the objectives and demands of many stakeholders. This implies that complex developmental issues can be solved holistically through interdisciplinary collaborative research.

Result shows (45.6%) that, there are barriers and challenges to interdisciplinary and collaborative research in Taraba state. These barriers include lack of adequate funding and sponsorship, dearth of sufficient research facilities and infrastructure, restricted access to valuable data and information, lack of collaborative culture, feeling of superiority/inferiority between and among researchers/disciplines and insufficient access to platforms for collaboration and communication. Leal, Tripathi, GinéGarriga & Willats (2018), recommended the critical role of higher education institutions in implementing and driving sustainable development initiatives through their institutional policies and practices. This is in line with the recommendation of Blessinger, Sengupta & Makhanya (2018) who highlighted the need for strategic contribution by academics to the SDGs for sustainable development. Olumide & Bada (2021), recommends that, facilities that facilitate quick and high-quality outcomes for all research projects should be established by the government and non-governmental groups. Collaborative research may be supported by fostering a collaborative culture inside academic institutions through joint appointments, interdisciplinary training programmes and acknowledgment of interdisciplinary accomplishments. The implication of the finding is that these obstacles can prevent interdisciplinary collaborative research in tackling complex societal challenges in Taraba state.

Furthermore, results (47%) showed that there are no instances where interdisciplinary and collaborative research was specifically employed in Taraba state. However, this contradicts the findings of Vincent & Kenneth (2014) who carried out research on how Nigerian food security is affected by climate change. The study used an interdisciplinary methodology that took into account how social, economic and environmental aspects are interdependent. By creating sustainable farming methods, the researchers enhanced food security and helped to realise SDG 2 - zero hunger. In 2016, Hwang & Jiwon carried out research on how Nigerian urbanisation affects health. An interdisciplinary methodology was used in the study to take into account the connections between public health and urban development. To address health disparities and help achieve SDG 3 - good health and well-being, the researchers created sustainable urban development plans. Similarly, a study on the effect of environmental education on sustainable development in Nigeria was carried out by Adenipekun & Ogunniyi (2015). An interdisciplinary methodology was used in the study to take into account the connections between environmental science and education. The researchers created environmental education initiatives that supported sustainable growth and helped achieve SDGs 13 - climate action and SDG 4, quality education. The findings showed that these instances show how interdisciplinary collaborative research has helped Nigeria achieve the SDGs in concrete ways.

Conclusion

Interdisciplinary collaborative research can play a vital role in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) not only in Taraba state, but Nigeria as whole. It is evident that effective interdisciplinary collaborative partnership highlights the advantages of combining many disciplines of study to curb difficult developmental and social issues, thereby resulting in the creation of long-lasting solutions that have a direct influence on

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achieving certain SDGs. This also emphasises how crucial it is to keep funding, encouraging and supporting interdisciplinary collaborative research projects within the Nigeria's academic community in order to accelerate the country's developmental efforts.

However, achieving the SDGs through interdisciplinary collaborative research has been hampered by myriad of challenges which range from lack of adequate funding and sponsorship, dearth of sufficient research facilities and infrastructure, restricted access, to lack of collaborative culture, feeling of superiority/inferiority between and among researchers/disciplines and insufficient access to platforms for collaboration and communication. Hence, strategic funds provision and allocation for interdisciplinary collaborative research, encouraging and cultivating collaborative culture between and among researchers/disciplines, adequate provision of research facilities and infrastructure, promotion of interdisciplinary collaborative research education and training, open access to valuable data and information for interdisciplinary and collaborative research and creating adequate platforms and opportunities for research collaboration and communication can to a large extent help surmount some of the challenges bedeviling interdisciplinary collaborative research in Nigeria.

Be that as it may, it is imperative that these suggestions are put into practice in order to foster interdisciplinary collaborative research atmosphere and to provide the next generation of researchers with the requisite knowledge and perspectives required towards propelling and accelerating sustainable development. Also, interdisciplinary collaborative research has the power to spur innovation and revolutionary changes across a range of industries. Hence, Nigeria can use the full potentials of interdisciplinary collaboration research to expedite the attainment of the SDGs at the state, national and international levels by surmounting the identified challenges and putting the suggested solutions into practice.

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